

The Case for a Maximum Tax: A Look at Some Legal, Economic and Ethical Issues

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Abstract

Several Congresses have passed various forms of minimum tax, both at the individual and corporate level. They have even passed alternative minimum tax bills to squeeze out additional tax revenue that would not otherwise be forthcoming. The problem was caused by the philosophy of taxation they have adopted over the years.

Rather than have the tax law function solely as a way to raise the revenue needed to keep the government running, various special interest groups and social do-gooders have persuaded Congress to incorporate much social engineering into the tax code. There are special provisions for oil companies, farmers, manufacturing companies, small business, homeowners, heads of household, families, sick people, blind people, people with children, and on and on.

This article will examine the other side of the coin. Whereas numerous commentators have been yapping about some kind of minimum tax in order to increase their perceived view of equity, no one is talking about establishing a maximum tax to ensure that no one pays too much more than their

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Special incentives are given to encourage individuals to alter their behavior in certain supposedly desirable ways. The problem is that if they respond to too many tax incentives, they will not pay "their fair share" of taxes. Thus the need for a minimum tax, to ensure that (almost) everybody who has income pays at least some income tax.

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The Two Philosophies of Taxation

There are only two philosophical bases upon which tax policy can be based. Curiously enough, elements of both of these contradictory philosophies are incorporated to some extent in most

tax systems.² One view is based on the ability to pay. To quote one of the biggest proponents of this view, "From each according to his abilities; to each according to his needs."³ Those who advance this position advocate policies like a graduated income tax, since they presume that the more money you make, the better able you are to pay. The question of whether anyone should pay based on ability to pay is never raised. When people go into the grocery store to buy a loaf of bread, the person behind the counter never asks how much they earn before quoting a price. A Rockefeller does not have to pay \$50,000 for a loaf that would sell to a poor person for \$0.10.⁴ The very thought is ridiculous. Yet that is the theory upon which the graduated income tax is based.

There are many utilitarian arguments against the graduated income tax.⁵ For example, it destroys incentives of the most productive people, the ones who can create jobs and increase capital, which is the only way to achieve economic growth. It causes distortion in the economy, since it alters economic behavior. It leads to a misallocation of resources and economic inefficiency.

There is also a moral argument against the graduated tax.⁶ It is exploitative. Thus, an appropriate name for the first theory of

² For discussions on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Some Tax Advice for Latvia and Other Similarly Situated Emerging Economies*, 13 INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER 223-308 (1996); Robert W. McGee, PRINCIPLES OF TAXATION FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES: SOME LESSONS FROM THE U.S. EXPERIENCE, 12 DICKINSON JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW 29-93 (1993).

³ KARL MARX, CRITIQUE OF THE GOTHA PROGRAM (1875). The original wording was "Jeder nach seinen Fähigkeiten, jedem nach seinen Bedürfnissen." Louis Blanc, the French socialist, said basically the same thing in 1848. GEORGE SELDES, THE GREAT THOUGHTS 274 (1985).

⁴ I owe this example to Murray N. Rothbard but I can't remember quite where I read it.

⁵ WALTER J. BLUM AND HARRY KALVEN, JR., THE UNEASY CASE FOR PROGRESSIVE TAXATION (1953); F.A. Hayek, *The Case Against Progressive Income Taxes*, FREEMAN 229-232 (1953).

⁶ Some would say that utilitarianism is a kind of moral philosophy. If it is, it is defective, for at least two reasons. Its premise is based on the greatest good for

taxation is the Exploitative Theory. It is based on the premise that the government has some inherent right to exploit its most productive citizens. This premise, in turn, is based on what political scientists might call the Master-Servant theory of the state, where the state is the master and the taxpayers are the servants. According to this theory, the state can extract whatever it wants from its subjects, since they owe fealty to the state.

The second theory of taxation might be called the Nonexploitative Theory, since it is not based on exploitation. This theory begins with the premise that the government is the servant and the people are the masters. The purpose of taxation is to pay for services that the people want, and the people should pay in proportion to the benefit they receive.

In its pure form, such taxation would include only user fees, which is not really taxation at all, if one defines a tax as the extraction of money by force. With user fees, the people who use the service are the ones who pay for it. Those who do not use the service are not forced to pay for it.

Charging a fee for gaining access to a public park is an example of a user fee. So would charging a fee to enter a public museum or a public library. Gasoline taxes would also be included under this heading.

User fees and lotteries are the only truly "fair" ways to finance government, since they are the only ways to raise revenue that do not include the use of force. User fees and lotteries are completely voluntary forms of public finance.

The problem with voluntary forms of public finance is that they do not raise sufficient revenue to pay for the bloated welfare

the greatest number. It incorporates positive-game theory. One problem with the utilitarian approach is that it is not possible to measure gains and losses accurately enough to determine whether the gains exceed the losses. Another problem -- one might call it a fatal flaw -- is that utilitarianism completely ignores property rights. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law & Economics*, 1 COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS 209-223 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, 14 NORTHWESTERN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW & BUSINESS 549-565 (1994).

states that presently exist. Thus, there is a need to resort to coercive forms of public finance.

The Case for a Maximum Tax

As long as politicians promise to give people something for nothing there will be a need to tax based on the Exploitation Theory of taxation. The problem inherent in such a system is that some people are forced to pay more than what they receive back in the form of government services. As a general rule, it might be said that poor people receive more in benefits from the tax system than what they pay into it and rich people receive less in services than what they pay in.

Leona Helmsley comes to mind as one example of a victim of the present Exploitation Theory of taxation. She paid about \$100 million in taxes, yet went to jail because some court determined that she "owed" a few million dollars more than that.⁷ Another example of a tax victim is Ross Perot. During one of the televised presidential debates, he said that he estimated that he paid about \$1 billion in taxes over the years.

It is hard to imagine that Ross Perot or Leona Helmsley received services from the federal government that was even remotely equal to the amount of individual income taxes they were forced to pay. They were clearly exploited.

What I advocate is as follows. Let's establish some maximum tax beyond which nobody is forced to pay. If it can be determined that individuals do not receive more than, say, \$20,000 in benefits from the federal government, let's establish a maximum tax that is some multiple of that amount. Ideally, the multiple should be one, since having a multiple of more than one would establish the legitimacy of exploitation.

However, since some people receive more than what they pay for and others receive less, as long as the tax system is not

⁷ United States v. Helmsley, 941 F.2d 71 (2d Cir. 1991). Interestingly enough, she actually received a refund because she paid too much tax. The reason she went to jail was because she submitted a fraudulent tax return.

based exclusively on user fees and lottery revenue, some people will continue to be exploited by government. That being the case, let's limit the amount of exploitation to perhaps twice the benefits received. Thus, if no one (or almost no one) receives more than \$20,000 in federal benefits, let's establish a maximum tax of \$40,000 per year. If we can't raise enough revenue to cover the cost of government services with a multiple of two, let's cut costs and eliminate government programs until we can raise the revenue that is needed to finance the bloated welfare state with a multiple of two.

Establishing a maximum tax would result in more than just a decrease in exploitation and an increase in equity. It would also eliminate the need for many people and businesses to keep tax records. If they know their tax is going to be no more than \$40,000, for example, people who have been paying substantially more than \$40,000 would just send a check to the government and be done with it. They would not have to retain the services of high priced accountants and tax attorneys to minimize their tax bill. These tax professionals would then be free to use their talent and energy doing something to increase economic growth rather than squandering their time trying to reduce government exploitation of their clients. A maximum tax would increase economic efficiency and equity. No one would be exploited by more than 100%, which is a reduction from the present levels of exploitation. It is not a perfect solution to exploitation but it is a step in the right direction.